

Microstructure development in novel titania-cobalt ferrite ceramic materials

Galizia Pietro, Baldisserri Carlo, Galassi Carmen*

¹CNR -ISTEC, Via Granarolo 64, I-48018 Faenza, Italy

*Corresponding author Galassi Carmen,

* email: carmen.galassi@istec.cnr.it; telephone: 0039 0546 699750

Co-author Galizia Pietro, email: pietro.galizia@istec.cnr.it

Co-author Baldisserri Carlo, email: carlo.baldisserri@istec.cnr.it

Abstract

The system cobalt ferrite (CFO) - titania (TO) has been studied in view to produce new in situ ceramic composites by conventional solid state reaction. To synthesize the CFO-TO composite, the processing parameters are optimized to yield a reliable and repeatable homogeneous distribution of the phases. Composition, crystalline structure and microstructure of the sintered bodies were investigated by XRD, SEM, microprobe analysis; the image analysis was performed to quantify the phases volume content and grain size. The final compositions after sintering differ significantly from the starting ones as a consequence of the reaction of titania with the ferrite and the formation of a new ternary compound $\text{Fe}_2\text{CoTi}_3\text{O}_{10}$ (FCTO). In this work we report for the first time the preparation of almost pure (about 95 vol%) single phase FCTO ceramics, its XRD patterns, and the microstructural characterization.

1 Highly densified and homogeneous composites were obtained with two to three phases
2 combined. Four different phase distributions are shown, depending on the starting
3 cobalt ferrite content.
4
5
6
7
8

9 Keywords: solid state reaction; in situ ceramic composite; ternary compound;
10
11 microstructure characterization;
12
13
14
15
16

17 **1. Introduction**

18 Heterostructures based on ferrites and titanates have been developed in several different
19 combinations of compositions and microstructures. Nowadays oxide heterostructures
20 ~~are receiving~~ increasing attention as they often let to devise new applications by tuning
21 or enhance certain properties [1]. In this view composite materials [2,3] ~~are~~ thoroughly
22 investigated and among them ferrites and their composites with dielectric, ferroelectric,
23 piezoelectric materials are currently ~~and~~ hot topic, in search of better properties. For
24 example magneto-dielectric composite materials ~~are attracting~~ increasing attention for
25 their application as substrates for miniaturization and efficiency enhancement of
26 antennas [4] while magnetoelectric composites materials are of interest in the smart
27 manufacturing and mechatronics fields as actuators/transducers, sensors, non-volatile
28 memories, etc. [5]. A growing number of papers ~~address~~ the topic in search of
29 compositions and microstructures matching the required combination of parameters for
30 the different working conditions, including magnetodielectric, magnetoelectric or, in
31 general, multifunctional materials with tailored macroscopic properties.
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52

53 Composite materials combining ceramic phases let to modulate different
54 magnetic/dielectric/ferroelectric properties by controlling the composition,
55 microstructure and interfaces formation. The properties of the composite are affected by
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 the number, type and volume ratio of the constituent phases, and may turn out to be an
2 average, a superposition, or a more complex combination of the properties of the ~~side~~
3 phases. It has been reported that the properties of these materials can be influenced by
4 the degree of interconnectivity and by specific interfacial phenomena [6-8].
5
6

7
8
9 Microstructure characterization of the sintered ceramics in terms of number, type and
10 volume ratio of the phases, grain size distribution, degree of interconnectivity, interfaces
11 and porosity, is crucial to understand how they influence the functional properties and to
12 achieving specific values of final properties [9-10].
13
14

15 A fundamental role in the structure and properties of ceramics is played by **starting**
16 **composition mixture**, shaping and densification processes. By varying the degrees of
17 chemical affinity a composite with the same starting phases, or with entirely new phases
18 can be obtained. The preparation routes must be carefully controlled in order to get two-
19 phase or multi-phase composites with ~~homogeneous~~ phase distribution and high density,
20 and with ~~homogeneous~~ microstructure correlated with the functional properties.
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35

36 ~~Stating form the above discussed scenery we~~ focused our attention on cobalt ferrite
37 (CoFe₂O₄) and titanium oxide (TiO₂), that have been investigated intensively for
38 decades owing to their excellent magnetic and dielectric properties: high coercivity and
39 magnetostriction coefficient for the CFO [11, 12], high static dielectric constants which
40 increase with decreasing temperature obeying a modified Curie-Weiss law, high
41 refractive index, incipient ferroelectricity and low-loss dielectric properties for TO
42 respectively [13-16]. However, to the best of our knowledge, no one has investigated
43 the reactivity of TiO₂ and CoFe₂O₄ mixtures heat treated at temperatures much higher
44 than about 600°C, at which the anatase-to-rutile conversion ~~averagely~~ occurs, no does
45 considerable literature exist documenting the properties of the compound Fe₂CoTi₃O₁₀
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

resulting from the reaction at high temperature of the two starting materials. The combination of such materials can be regarded as a useful, preliminary approach in the search of novel multifunctional materials for many applications. Moreover it is of most interest as a study of the cobalt ferrite titanium oxide reactivity, propaedeutic to the investigation of the interaction between titanates with ferrites as very often, at least limited reaction between the two phases significantly influence the final properties of the composite material.

In this work, we focus on the preparation and microstructural characterization of ceramic composites obtained starting from TiO₂ and CoFe₂O₄ powder mixtures. The samples was prepared by the conventional solid state reaction process, with TO/CFO molar ratios from 0.73 to 11.75. In this paper we report the study of the reactions and the resulting phases depending on the starting CFO/TO ratio. Microstructure and composition of the composites have been intensively studied and are discussed here.

2. Materials and methods

Cobalt ferrite (CFO) powders with CoFe₂O₄ composition were obtained by reacting Co₃O₄ (nano powder Aldrich 637025), and Fe₂O₃ (Aldrich nano powder 544884) powder mixtures at 800 °C for 4 h, and then performing planetary milling of the calcined products in ethanol medium for 2.5 h using zirconia jar with 250 cm³ volume, zirconia balls of 5 mm of diameter and a fixed speed of 400 rpm. The milling media to powder mass ratio was 4:1. The pure crystalline CFO powders were mixed with commercial TiO₂ powder (Degussa P25) according to the compositional scheme (100-x)TO-x CFO, with $x = 0, 20.0, 30.0, 33.5, 40.0, 44.0, 49.5, 57.2, 80.0$ and 100 wt %.

In Table 1 the starting composition of the samples is reported as weight and molar percentages of the starting CFO content and the corresponding TO/CFO molar fraction. The correlation between samples' IDs and initial percent weight of CFO (x) is also shown.

Sample identification	Starting CFO (wt.%)	Starting CFO (mol %)	TO/CFO (mol/mol)
TO	0	0	-
CFT20	20	7.84	11.75
CFT30	30	12.73	6.85
CFT33	33.5	14.65	5.83
CFT40	40	18.50	4.41
CFT44	44	21.07	3.75
FCTO	49.5	25.00	3.00
CFT57	57.2	31.29	2.20
CFT80	80	57.66	0.73
CFO	100	100	0

Table 1. Starting compositions of the materials.

Powder mixtures were wet ball-milled, dried and subjected to cold linear pressing at 70 MPa to produce 30 mm diameter, 2-3 mm thick disks. Isostatic pressing at 250 MPa was applied to the disks to obtain green homogeneous CFT bodies, which were then sintered in air at 1200 °C for 2 h. A constant heating rate of 150 °C/h was employed to reach the sintering temperature plateau, and the sintered samples were brought back to room temperature by natural cooling of the furnace. After sintering, the ceramic bodies were ground to remove the surface layers in order to ensure a reliable X-ray analysis. The particle size measurements of the as calcined CFO powders and the post milled ones - in terms of equivalent spherical diameters based on settling velocity ('velocity ESD') - were determined with a Micromeritics SediGraph 5100. Samples were prepared by diluting 1.50 g of CFO powder in 75 mL of 0.1 M Calgon dispersing solution, giving a sample concentration of 20 g l⁻¹ ($\approx 0.4\%$ by volume) and then sonified for 1 min immediately before analysis. The data collection was made with standard Micromeritics

1 software (version 2.00) and the density distribution was calculated as the derivative of
2 the measured cumulative mass percentage ~~finer~~ with respect to the velocity ESD
3 (particles size) and was approximated using finite intervals [17]. The formation of the
4 new phase FCTO from titania and cobalt ferrite was studied by differential scanning
5 calorimetry (DSC), using a Netzsch STA 409 calorimeter, increasing the temperature of
6 the TO-CFO stoichiometric powder mixture - held in an alumina crucible ~~like~~ the
7 reference alumina powder - up to 1200 °C at the heating rate of 3 °C/min.

8 Phase compositions of the calcined and sintered samples and their relative phase
9 volumes were determined by combining SEM, EDS and XRD data. XRD patterns were
10 obtained at room temperature on a Bruker D8 X-ray diffractometer (θ - θ) using Cu K α
11 radiation in the range $15^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 70^\circ$ and a 2.4°/min scanning rate. The average
12 crystallite sizes were calculated using Debye Scherrer formula $D = (k \lambda / \beta \cos\vartheta)$, where
13 D is the average crystallite size derived from the highest peak of the XRD pattern, k is
14 the sphere shape factor (k = 0.9), ϑ is the Braggs angle, β is the Full Width at Half
15 Maximum (FWHM) of the peak and λ is the wavelength of X-ray ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) used.
16 Following this formula, the XRD calculation does not give the true average crystal size
17 but an apparent one, ~~which, anyway, depends on the first.~~

18 Morphology, phase compositions, porosity and grain size distribution were investigated
19 by SEM analysis of polished sections performed on a FEI Quanta 200 ESEM™
20 scanning electron microscopy system. The EDS analysis was performed on the polished
21 surface positioned at 8.5 μm working distance and applying 12 kV accelerating voltage.
22 The relative density of the sintered samples was calculated, as the ratio between the
23 samples' density (determined by the Archimedes' method) and the theoretical density
24 estimated from the phases detected by XRD diffractograms and the stoichiometry of the
25 starting powders. The relative density was calculated also through the analysis of the
26

1 back-scattered electrons (BSE) images using the software Image-Pro Analyzer 7.0 to
2 calculate the area covered by pores and by each component phase, identified by SEM-
3 EDS analysis [18, 19]. Assuming a shape factor of the grains and pores of one, i.e.
4 assuming no preferential orientation of the grains of any of the detected phases, by
5 image analysis coupled with a SEM-EDS analysis, the phases were identified and the
6 volumetric fraction quantified from the ratio of the number of pixels attributed to a
7 specific phase to the total number of pixels in the image. The grain size was determined
8 by the linear intercept method. The relative frequencies and the linked normalised
9 cumulative frequencies were obtained by stratified sampling, i.e. by dividing the grain
10 size population into ten consecutive and non-overlapping 1- μm wide bins, with a step of
11 one micron, before sampling.
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

29 **3. Results and discussion**

30 **Powder synthesis**

31 Synthesis of cobalt ferrite from iron oxide nanopowder produces coarse, partially
32 sintered and slow-reacting cobalt ferrite (CFO) powders already upon reaction at 800
33 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, so that a milling step is required before further mixing with titania (TO) powder.
34 Therefore, in order to enhance reactivity, the in-house prepared cobalt ferrite was first
35 ground, and its particle size distribution (PSD) and average crystallite size (D) were
36 calculated. The size distribution is not narrow as the PSD is characterized by an average
37 particle size (1th moment, $d_{1/0}$) of 19 μm and a volume mean diameter (4th/3th moment
38 ratio, $d_{4/3}$) of 37 μm . By comparing them with the starting values of $d_{1/0}$ and $d_{4/3}$, 25 μm
39 and 58 μm respectively, a reduction of average particle size of 24% and a shift to lower
40 size of the PSD curve is achieved. The enhanced reactivity of the CFO powder -
41 according to the Read-Shockley equation - was confirmed by the reduction of D, which
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 decreased from 76 nm to 50 nm after milling. Said reductions give a positive
2 contribution in the cold consolidation and densification steps. The DSC analysis
3 performed on TO powder mixed in stoichiometric amount with CFO for the formation
4 of $\text{Fe}_2\text{CoTi}_3\text{O}_{10}$ (FCTO) (molar ratio 3 : 1) is shown in Fig. 1. The DSC analysis shows
5 an endothermic peak at 794.8 °C, in agreement with the results of Jones et al. on the
6 formation of FCTO, which only starts when the TO has been fully converted to rutile
7 [20].
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19

44 **Fig. 1** DSC analysis on powder with composition 50.5 wt.% TO and 49.5 wt.% CFO
45

46
47
48 FCTO formation was also verified by XRD analysis on the same powder mixture after
49 calcination at 700 °C and at 950 °C for 4 h, the XRD patterns being reported in Fig. 2.
50
51 In the same figure, the patterns of stoichiometric CFO powder calcined at 800 °C and
52 the pure TO (rutile), CFO, and FCTO heat- treated at the sintering temperature are
53
54 reported as well. The analysis of the FCTO diffractograms shows that at 700 °C the TO
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 is fully converted to rutile while the reaction with the CFO is not started yet, the only
2 peaks of TO and CFO phases being present. After calcination at 950 °C for 4 h, the
3 FCTO powder mixture is almost completely converted to FCTO, with only small
4 quantities of unreacted TO and CFO phases left. The reaction between Co_3O_4 and Fe_2O_3
5 and the formation of CFO were also tested on powders calcined at 800 °C. The result,
6 also shown in Fig. 2, proves full conversion of reactants in the spinel solid solution
7 during calcination, with accurate to within $\sim\pm 3$ wt.% . The formation of a single CFO
8 phase is expected from the Fe-Co-O pseudobinary phase diagrams by Takahashi et al.
9 [21].
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24

25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of sintered TO, FCTO and CFO materials, and calcined powders with CFO = 49.5 wt. %, at 700 °C (FCTO powder 700), and 950 °C (FCTO powder 950) compared to pure CFO powder (CFO powder 800).

Microstructure of the sintered materials

1 Results from X-Ray diffraction analysis of $(100-x)\text{TO} - x\text{CFO}$ ceramics composites,
2 with $x = 0, 20, 30, 40, 49.5, 57.2, 80$ and 100 wt.%, are shown in Fig. 3.
3

4 The XRD diffractograms show that the sintered composites can be classified in four
5 different classes. For the composites with TO/CFO molar ratios from 3.75 to 11.75
6 (class I), the observed Bragg reflections match the reported values for rutile and iron
7 cobalt titanium oxide (FCTO), belonging to the space group $P4_2/mnm$ and $Bbmm$,
8 respectively (Powder Diffraction Files, cards no 21-1276 and 41-213, respectively). In
9 Fig. 3 one can observe that in the samples CFT20, CFT30 and CFT40 the height of the
10 peaks related to the TO phase decreases and that of the FCTO phase increases, both in a
11 gradual fashion.
12
13

14 FCTO and CFO phases (cards no 41-213 and 22-1086, respectively) were found in the
15 sample with the TO/CFO molar ratio of 2.2 (class III), whilst cobalt titanium oxide with
16 ilmenite structure (CTO, card no 15-866) and hematite (FO, card no 33-0664) were
17 found in the sample with the molar ratio TO/CFO of 0.73 (class IV). No Bragg
18 reflection associated with the FCTO was found in the sample CFT80. In CFO and TO
19 ceramic samples, a single phase was observed, whilst the FCTO sample retained traces
20 of unreacted TO and CFO (class II).
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 3 XRD patterns of TO, CFT20, CFT30, CFT40, FCTO, CFT57, CFT80 and CFO materials, sintered at 1200 °C for 2 h

In Figs 4, 5, 6 and 7 SEM micrographs of the CFO-TO ceramic composites sintered at 1200 °C for 2 h are shown. The BSE images of polished surfaces show that all compositions have two or more homogeneously dispersed phases, as expected from XRD patterns, and a small amount of porosity, the latter corresponding to black regions. XRD phases identification was corroborated by EDS which was performed for each sample on grains of different shades of grey (showed in the BackScattered Electrons micrographs) and classified in different classes in function of the detected elements and in agreement with the XRD results. In this way the minor variations of colour, due to a different lattice orientation, were distinguished from the different colours due to the different phase density. Therefore the image analysis was performed by de-convoluting the pixels distribution depending on their shade of grey and partial integrating of each

1 populations of pixels associated to a specific phase. The results of the data processing
2 are shown in the Fig. 8 as dots (circles for FCTO, rhombuses for CFO; triangles for TO;
3
4 squares for CTO and crosses for FO) representing the calculated volume percentage of
5
6 the detected phase in the sintered sample.
7
8
9

44 **Fig. 4** BSE SEM images of class I: CFT20 (a), CFT30 (b), CFT33 (c), and CFT40 (d).
45
46 All length bars: 20 μm
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 5 BSE SEM images of FCTO sample (class II). Length bar: 20 μm

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 6 BSE SEM images of CFT57 sample (class III). Length bar: 20 μm

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 7 BSE SEM images of CFT80 sample (class IV). Length bar: 20 μm

Fig. 8 Percent phase volumes vs. CFO content in starting powder mixtures. The vertical lines at about 49.5 and 74.6 wt.% correspond to TO/CFO molar ratio of 3 and 1 respectively.

In Fig.8, it can be seen that there is a good correlation between i) the measured and the theoretical phase volumes, where the last ones were calculated from the phases identified by XRD diffraction, ii) the ratios of the starting powders and the reactions that are proposed in the following (Table 2). In samples with TO/CFO molar ratios higher than 3, the peaks of TO and FCTO phases appear, whilst at lower TO/CFO molar ratios - up to 2.2, CFO was observed instead of TO. This means that in the TO/CFO $\geq$ 2.2 compositional range FCTO is the most stable phase, whilst when the TO/CFO ratio is smaller or larger than 3, TO and the CFO are the limiting reagents, respectively. FCTO forms from three moles of TO and one mole of CFO at temperatures higher than 800 °C. At TO/CFO = 0.73, CTO is the most stable phase, and TO is the limiting

reagent. The four different classes are summarized in the following reaction schemes (Table 2).

$a\text{TiO}_2 + b\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4 \rightarrow c\text{Fe}_2\text{CoTi}_3\text{O}_{10} + d\text{CoTiO}_3 + e\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + f\text{TiO}_2 + g\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4$						
Class	a/b	c	d	e	f	g
I	3 - 11.75	= b	= 0	= 0	= a - 3 b	= 0
II	3	~ b	= 0	= 0	~ 0	~ 0
III	2.2 - 3	= $1/3 a$	= 0	= 0	= 0	= $b - 1/3 a$
IV	0.73	= 0	= a	= a	= 0	= $b - a$

Table 2 – Reaction schemes

It is important to note that 11.75 and 2.2 are not the limiting (a/b) ratios for the theoretical reactions, but the experimentally verified ones (theoretical black lines in Fig.8). Most probably, the first reaction takes place for higher values of the (a/b) ratio than 11.75 too, and the third reaction for (a/b) values lower than 2.2. At the same time, the last class of composite most probably appears in a wide (a/b range) about 0.73 and anyway smaller than 1, as may be surmised looking at the theoretical grey line drawn in the Fig. 8. The FCTO phase is formed as the a/b ratio approaches the value of 3, but in the sample with this stoichiometry a small amount of powder remained unreacted. From image analysis, it can be concluded that –for each mole of cobalt ferrite– there are 2.8 moles of titania instead of 3. This result is in close agreement with the expected reaction taking place, especially if one considers that –from all image analysis data– a smaller amount of titania was found. This is perhaps due to the presence of some titania agglomeration in the samples that does not show up in the polished surface, an assumption that also explains the higher relative density values obtained by image analysis (Fig. 9). This can be due to the presence of macroporosity under the polished surface.

The relative density and percent phase volume data obtained by image analysis are in agreement with the relative density obtained with Archimedes' method, and with

1 theoretical percent volume, respectively. This corroborates the soundness of image
2 analysis, and supports the adequacy of the proposed reactions in describing the
3 phenomena that occur during sintering. In Fig. 9 the relative density determined both by
4 Archimede's method and by image analysis are plotted as a function of the starting
5 cobalt ferrite content; the figure shows that the residual porosity depends linearly on the
6 starting cobalt ferrite content and it is independent from the different phases formation
7 which brings to a discontinuous theoretical density curve (Fig. 9). The linear correlation
8 of the amount of porosity with the starting cobalt ferrite content can be ascribed to the
9 oxygen evolution during sintering which leaves spherical pores (Fig.s 4, 5, 6 and 7),
10 according to the following reactions [22]:
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23

26 as a consequence of traces of unreacted cobalt oxide and iron oxide not detected in the
27 XRD pattern of the calcined powders.
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 9 Relative and theoretical density vs. CFO content in starting powder mixtures.

The trend of the theoretical density curve (Fig.9) is reflected on the volumetric changes resulting from the chemical reaction (Fig.10) and on the resulting stresses. In some compositions few micro-fractures appear that can be seen in the SEM images (Figs. 4, 5 and 6); a correlation of the extent of such cracks with the different phases formation, which brings to a discontinuous theoretical density curve, can be established. In fact, reporting the variation in volume in function of the starting composition (Fig.10), the correlation between the cracks concentration and the FCTO formation is evident, as the most damaged samples are the FCTO and CFT57 (Figs. 5 and 6, respectively) to which corresponds an expansion percentage of 5.1% and 4.3%, respectively; while no crack are observed in the sample CFT80 even if it get a shrinkage of 3.7%, the third largest in absolute value.

Fig. 10 Variations in volume predicted from the chemical reactions reported in Table 2.

Under the above-mentioned sintering conditions, the pure FCTO phase formed from the stoichiometric mixture of three moles of TO and one mole of CFO shows larger grains if compared to those formed from non-stoichiometric mixtures (Fig. 5). This can perhaps be attributed to the lack of pinning effect exerted by the grains of the unreacted phase (in excess of the $[CFO] + 3[TO] = [FCTO]$ stoichiometry) that is present when the starting composition is non-stoichiometric. The residual CFO and TO are shown by the white and dark grey grains, respectively, in Fig. 5. In Fig. 11 the grain size density distribution curves are reported. They show the first derivative of the normalised cumulative frequencies with respect to the grain size of different composites. For all compositions, no grain larger than $8 \mu\text{m}$ was observed. The value of the grain size corresponding to the highest frequency is $3 \mu\text{m}$ for the composites with a molar ratio $TO/CFO \geq 3$ and $2 \mu\text{m}$ for the others ($TO/CFO < 3$). The degree of symmetry of the

1 differential grain size distribution curve depends on the starting composition too. In fact,
2 a loss of symmetry in the left side of the distribution (low grain size region) appears,
3 which can be ascribed to the pinning effect exerted by the presence of unreacted phase
4 for all the compositions, the exception being the FCTO sample, which yields the most
5 symmetrical dispersion curve. Further, the pinning effect exerted by the CFO grains
6 looks greater than the one from TO grains. It can be due to the larger size of the CFO
7 starting powder compared to the TO powder (Degussa P25). In the right side of the
8 distribution curves, the grain size larger than 5 micron could still be correlated to the
9 starting size of the CFO. The differences in the shape of the curves between 4 microns
10 and 8 microns is more difficult to account for, and could be attributed to different
11 mechanisms and densification kinetics for the different compositions rather than to the
12 particle size of the starting CFO. It is important to note that where the reaction was
13 more homogeneous, as for the FCTO, the distribution is more symmetrical and the
14 average grain size is larger (about 3.6 μm for the FCTO), while where the reaction was
15 less homogeneous, in terms of new phases formation and unreacted phases amount, as
16 for the CFT80, where three new phases are formed, the distribution is less symmetrical
17 and the average grain size is smaller (about 2.5 μm). For the CFT80 composite, the
18 smaller average grain size is due to the decomposition of CFO in iron oxide (FO) and
19 cobalt monoxide which reacts with the TO forming the CTO [23]. It is worthy to remark
20 that the particle size of the CFO starting powder could play a main role in diffusion at
21 grain boundaries and/or volume diffusion, since larger particle size increases the
22 diffusion distance and makes the sintering more difficult.

Fig. 11 Normalized grain size distribution density calculated on 100 grains per composition

4. Conclusions

A series of cobalt ferrite-titania ceramic composites have been successfully prepared by the solid-state reaction method. The effect of the initial TO/CFO molar ratio, on the phase composition and microstructure has been thoroughly investigated. The ferrite and titania react to form different phases and four compositional ranges can be identified:

FCTO-TO composites with a percent volume of FCTO from 40 % to 90 %; FCTO-CFO composites with FCTO percent volume from 87 % to 90 %; FCTO-TO-CFO and CTO-FO-CFO composites with 2.5 and 20.4 % volume of magnetic CFO phase, respectively.

In addition to controlling the percent volume of the phases by changing the CFO/TO mass ratio, we found an inverse correlation between porosity and starting powders' TO/CFO molar ratio. The formation of the FCTO phase, which occurs at about 800°C, leads to the onset of cracks due to the expansion that exceed 5 vol.% when the TO/CFO

1 molar ratio is stoichiometric; while as the starting powders' TO/CFO molar ratio is not
2 stoichiometric the limiting reagents make a pinning effect bringing to finer
3
4 microstructure. All these results confirm the above discussed equilibrium phases and
5
6 provide valuable insight in view of designing of ceramic composites with specific
7
8 percent volumes of magnetic/dielectric phase, by simply altering the weight ratios of
9
10 component powders.
11
12
13
14
15

16 **Acknowledgements**

17
18 The authors gratefully acknowledge the skilful contribution of Mr. C. Capiani (CNR-
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

26 **References**

- 29 [1] Gregory S, Rohrer et al. Challenges in ceramic science: a report from the workshop
30 on emerging research areas in ceramic science. *J Am Ceram Soc* 2012; 95:3699–3712.
31
32 DOI: 10.1111/jace.12033
33
34
35
36 [2] Hrib LM, Caltun OF. Effects of the chemical composition of the magnetostrictive
37 phase on the dielectric and magnetoelectric properties of cobalt ferrite-barium titanate
38
39 composites. *J Alloys Compd* 2011; 509: 6644-6648. DOI:
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [3] Xu QQ, Feng JT, Li LC, X QS, Wang J. Hollow ZnFe₂O₄/TiO₂ composites: High-
performance and recyclable visible-light photocatalyst. *J Alloys Compd* 2015; 641:110-
118. DOI: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.04.076
- [4] Su H, Tang X, Zhang H, Jing Y, Bai F. Low-loss magneto-dielectric materials:
approaches and developments. *J Electron Mater* 2014; 43:299-307.

- 1 [5] Nan C-W, Bichurin M I, Dong, Viehland D, Srinivasan G. Multiferroic
2 magnetoelectric composites: Historical perspective, status, and future directions. J Appl
3 Phys 2008; 103: 031101. doi: 10.1063/1.2836410
4
5 [6] Chung DDL. Composite materials science and applications. Springer Science; 2010.
6
7 [7] Aldrigo M, Bianchini D, Costanzo A, Masotti D, Galassi C. Exploitation of a novel
8 magneto-dielectric substrate for miniaturization of wearable UHF antennas. Mater Lett
9 2012; 87:127-130.
10
11 [8] Mukherjee D, Hordagoda M, Lampen P, Phan M-H, Srikanth H, Witanachchi S,
12 Mukherjee P. Simultaneous enhancements of polarization and magnetization in epitaxial
13 $\text{Pb}(\text{Zr}_{0.52}\text{Ti}_{0.48})\text{O}_3/\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ multiferroic heterostructures enabled by ultrathin
14 CoFe_2O_4 sandwich layers. Phys Rev B 2015; 91:054419.
15
16 DOI:10.1103/PhysRevB.91.054419
17
18 [9] Karilainen AO, Ikonen PM, Simovski CR, Tretyakov SA. Choosing dielectric or
19 magnetic material to optimize the bandwidth of miniaturized resonant antennas. IEEE
20 Trans Antennas Propag 2011; 59:3991-3998.
21
22 [10] Zheng H, Wang J, Lofland SE, Ma Z, Mohaddes-Ardabili L, Zhao T, Salamanca-
23 Riba L, Shinde SR, Ogale SB, Bai F, Viehland D, Jia Y, Schlom DG, Wuttig M,
24 Roytburd A, Ramesh R. Multiferroic $\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-CoFe}_2\text{O}_4$ nanostructures. Science 2004;
25 303: 661-663. DOI: 10.1126/science.1094207
26
27 [11] Haneda K, Morrish AH. Noncollinear magnetic structure of CoFe_2O_4 small
28 particles. J Appl Phys 1988; 63:4258-4262.
29
30 [12] Rajendrana M, Pullara RC, Bhattacharyaa AK, Dasb D, Chintalapudib SN,
31 Majumdar CK. Magnetic properties of nanocrystalline CoFe_2O_4 powders prepared at
32 room temperature: variation with crystallite size. J Magn Magn Mater 2001; 232:71-83.
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1 [13] Samara GA, Peercy PS. Pressure and temperature dependence of the static
2 dielectric constants and raman spectra of TiO₂ (rutile). Phys Rev B 1973; 7:1131-1148.
3
4 [14] Batool SS, Imran Z, Rafiq MA, Hasan MM, Willander M. Investigation of
5 dielectric relaxation behavior of electrospun titanium dioxide nanofibers using
6
7 temperature dependent impedance spectroscopy. Ceram Int 2013;139:1775-1783. DOI:
8
9 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.08.024>
10
11
12 [15] Lee C. Lattice dynamics and dielectric properties of incipient ferroelectric TiO₂
13 rutile. Phys Rev B 1994; 50:13379-13387.
14
15 [16] Marinel S, Choi DH, Heuguet R, Agrawal D, Lanagan M. Broadband dielectric
16 characterization of TiO₂ ceramics sintered through microwave and conventional
17 processes. Cerm Int 2013; 39:299-306. DOI:
18
19 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.06.025>
20
21 [17] Sommer K. 40 Years of presentation particle size distribution – yet still incorrect?
22 Part Part Syst Charact 2001; 18:22-25.
23
24 [18] Toll S, Andersson PO. Microstructural characterization of injection moulded
25 composites using image analysis. Composites 1991; 22:299-306.
26
27 [19] Allard B, Sotin C. Determination of mineral phase percentages in granular rocks by
28 image analysis on a microcomputer. Comput Geosci 1988; 14:261-269.
29
30 [20] Jones S, Lake B. Iridescent magnetic effect pigments. United States Patent
31 Application Publication 2008; US 2008/0280150 A1.
32
33 [21] Takahashi M, Fine ME. Coercive force of spinodally decomposed cobalt ferrite
34 with excess cobalt. J Amer Ceram Soc 1970; 53:633-634.
35
36 [22] Aukrust E, Muan A. Iron and stell division – thermodynamic properties of solid
37 solution with spinel-type structure: II. Trans Met Soc AIME 1964; 230:378-383.
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

[23] Inagaki M, Naka S. Decomposition of Co_2TiO_4 spinel below 1000 K. J Solid State Chem 1975; 13:365-367.

Figure's captions

Fig. 1 DSC analysis on powder with composition 50.5 wt.% TO and 49.5 wt.% CFO

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of sintered TO, FCTO and CFO materials, and calcined powders with CFO = 49.5 wt. %, at 700 °C (FCTO powder 700), and 950 °C (FCTO powder 950) compared to pure CFO powder (CFO powder 800)

Fig. 3 XRD patterns of TO, CFT20, CFT30, CFT40, FCTO, CFT57, CFT80 and CFO materials, sintered at 1200 °C for 2 h

Fig. 4 BSE SEM images of class I: CFT20 (a), CFT30 (b), CFT33 (c), and CFT40 (d). All length bars: 20 μm

Fig. 5 BSE SEM images of FCTO sample (class II). Length bar: 20 μm

Fig. 6 BSE SEM images of CFT57 sample (class III). Length bar: 20 μm

Fig. 7 BSE SEM images of CFT80 sample (class IV). Length bar: 20 μm

Fig. 8 Percent phase volumes vs. CFO content in starting powders mixtures. The vertical lines at about 49.5 and 74.6 wt.% correspond to TO/CFO molar ratio of 3 and 1 respectively.

Fig. 9 Relative and theoretical density vs. CFO content in starting powder mixtures

Fig. 10 Variations in volume predicted from the chemical reaction reported in Table 2